

Approaching the Finish Line Development of the 2nd Gen Eurocode 3 and What's Next?

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ABSTRACT

The development of the second-generation Eurocode 3 is approaching the finish line. About half of the general parts, i.e., EN 1993-1, have already been published by CEN; and for the application parts, i.e. EN 1993-2 to -6, the final technical commentary phase, the so-called CEN Enquiry, is currently underway. A good time to reflect on what has been achieved and plan the next steps. The 2nd Gen Eurocode 3 is a consistent continuation of the current generation, which was published almost 20 years ago and is currently being used successfully in engineering practice. The future steel structures standard focuses on the users and their workflow in design, enhances clarity and the degree of harmonization, and thus increases application-friendliness and ease of use. To a certain extent, the 2nd Gen Eurocode 3 also represents a transition in a changing world of global challenges: It has already a decisive contribution to sustainable building and infrastructures for the important future topics of mitigating climate change and resource conservation by taking into account innovations such as the extension of the scope of application to high-strength structural steels and the improvement of structural efficiency by adapting the design rules. Moreover, 2nd Gen Eurocode 3 also started to address state-of-the-art technological developments with the design of steel structures using finite element calculations and its normative guidance of design-by-analysis or the Direct Design Method (DDM) initiated with the new Part 1-14. These initiated developments in design standards must be consistently continued and strengthened in the future. With regard to technological developments, the focus is on dealing with big data and artificial intelligence in standardization and design, as well as the design of additively manufactured steel structures. The future strategy of Eurocode 3 also addresses the contribution to sustainability in the construction sector in terms of the UNs Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and measures to mitigate climate change in line with the EU Green Deal by promoting circularity through appropriate normative rules for (i) the assessment and retrofitting of existing iron and steel structures and (ii) the design of reclaimed steel components for reuse.

Keywords: 2nd Gen Structural Eurocodes, Eurocode 3, circular eternity, technological developments

1 STANDARDS IN A CHANGING WORLD OF GLOBAL CHALLENGES

In recent years, a trivial insight has become established in society's consciousness and in political action: we need to preserve and conserve what we have in a world with finite resources and limited and slow natural renewal. Nevertheless, growth and the desire for something new continue to characterize human activity in order to maintain or even improve the desired quality of life. As a result, emissions, energy and resource consumption, and waste volumes continue to rise worldwide. Therefore, we must focus our technological, economic, and social capabilities even more strongly on enabling everyone in the world to live a life of prosperity and fulfillment now and in the future without exceeding the earth's capacity.

In this regard, the construction sector plays a significant role due to its inherently high consumption of resources. Around 37 % of CO₂ emissions, 36 % of energy consumption (1), and 32 % of mineral extraction (2) can be attributed to construction activities worldwide. Around 37 % of the waste generated in Europe originates from construction (3). Hence, the construction industry is facing new challenges with the current debate on climate change mitigation measures, consumption of primary resources, and waste avoidance. The sector needs to create innovative solutions that relate to a number of global challenges and the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as well as the objectives of the EU's Green Deal to become climate neutral by 2050. It is imperative that sustainable and future-oriented construction take the enormous building and bridge stock into account in the solution. First and foremost, the functionality and use of the existing stock must be guaranteed in the long term. Wherever possible, the existing structures should be reused and/or recycled subsequently if further use in their current form is no longer necessary or desirable, or if refurbishment and retrofitting is no longer worthwhile from an overall economic or sustainability perspective. Despite the above prioritization, the assessment of existing structures must also take into account considerations regarding the optimal time for the reuse of the existing building and bridge stock, known as urban mining in construction. Nowadays, the end of use of a building or infrastructure is often not determined by reaching the scheduled service life but by changing requirements and deficiencies in functional performance despite a largely intact load-bearing structure. It can, therefore, be utilized that the load-bearing capacity of the individual structural components and their structural integrity in building structures are usually still present after the scheduled service life, typically 50 years (4). However, it is not possible to fully cover the demand for new construction from reused structural components. In addition, the global challenge of climate change and the construction industry's significant contribution to finding a solution cannot be viewed in isolation. Given (i) the continued population growth of almost 2 billion people, (ii) the increase in urbanization from 5 to 7 out of 10 people in urban areas both in the next 25 years, and (iii) the aging infrastructure in large parts of the world, there will be a huge further increase in demand for construction services, even with a fundamental understanding of and commitment to reduction and renouncement. A systematic combination of measures is therefore required to ensure that the construction sector will make a significant contribution to mitigating climate change while at the same time tackling social challenges and making a decisive contribution to solving other global challenges. The global challenges are transnational in nature and transinstitutional in solution. They require collaborative action among governments, international organizations, corporations, universities and creative individuals. By (a) specifying requirements for products, services or processes, (b) thus creating transparency about their properties, (c) guaranteeing quality and (d) ensuring the safety of people and property, standards are a strong instrument to support the achievement, Fig. 1. For instance, standards are an effective instrument for disseminating smart technical solutions to mitigate climate change and global challenges, creating acceptance for them and, creating legal certainty for the solutions in order to establish planning security. The second generation of the Structural Eurocodes, including Eurocode 3, aims to make already a decisive contribution to sustainable building structures and infrastructures for the important future-oriented topics of climate neutrality and resource conservation. This is to be achieved, among other things, by (i) taking account of and promoting innovations and (ii) improving structural efficiency by adapting and further developing the design rules. At the same time, a framework was created for the development of future generations of design standards, e.g. 3rd Gen Structural Eurocodes, that take into account the necessity and social need to take greater account of anthropogenic climate change and measures to reduce carbon emissions in all sectors, including the construction sector.

Fig. 1. Tasks of standards in a changing world: link between standards and SDGs.

2 THE 2ND GENERATION OF EUROCODE 3

2.1 General

The development of the second generation of the Structural Eurocodes is approaching the finish line. The English language versions of about half of the general parts of Eurocode 3, i.e., EN 1993-1, have already been published by CEN and the National Annexes are currently being prepared in many countries. For the application parts, i.e. EN 1993-2 to -6, the final technical commentary phase, the so-called CEN Enquiry, is currently underway, Fig. 2. For some parts, the responsible Working Groups are already planning so-called early amendments, either to supplement technical content that has been generally accepted for some time but was not yet ready for implementation in the so-called Formal Vote version or to make essential technical changes and editorial and technical corrections. It is time for the committee responsible for Eurocode 3, CEN/TC 250/SC 3, to reflect on what has been achieved and to plan the next steps.

2.2 Background and procedure for the development

The publication of the existing 10 Structural Eurocode parts of the so-called first generation took place between 2002 and 2007 and represented a great success and the culmination of over 30 years of joint development work. The Eurocodes influence the daily work of around half a million professional engineers throughout Europe (5), (6). Nationally Determined Parameters (NDPs) are available in the form of National Annexes to allow all countries to define their desired level of reliability and safety and to take account of geographical and climatic specifics. As a consequence, in some countries, the former national standards were only replaced by the Eurocodes after 2010. Long-term confidence in and acceptance of the standards require appropriate further development of the Structural Eurocodes. The work program for the 2nd generation of the Eurocodes focuses on ensuring that the standards remain up to date by incorporating new methods and materials and taking into account current regulatory and market requirements. In addition, the revision work focuses on further harmonization and improving the application-friendliness and ease-of-use of the Eurocodes for engineering practitioners in daily practice.

Fig. 2. Detailed revision process for EN 1993 and planned time schedule for the parts of EN 1993.

The further evolution of the Eurocodes is partly done within the scope of the general revision and maintenance as a usual procedure for a code revision according to CEN. These revisions are launched in the form of a call for systematic reviews of the National Standardization Bodies (NSBs). However, the Eurocodes' further evolution took place largely within the scope of mandate M/515, which was agreed upon between the European Commission and CEN in 2012. Among the objectives of the mandate is the extension of the Eurocode rules to new materials, products, and construction methods, improving their practical use for day-to-day calculations, and achieving better harmonization, not least by reducing the number of NDPs. The technical enhancements were realized by so-called Project Teams (PTs) that consisted of four to six members.

The CEN/TC 250 work program related to mandate M/515 was divided into four technically and temporally overlapping phases (Fig. 3(b)). This was done to effectively manage the interdependencies between activities and ensure that the work was undertaken efficiently. However, at the end of the term of the M/515 mandate and the work of the Project Teams, the work on the draft standards was not yet complete. Responsibility for finalizing the so-called formal vote drafts then lay with the various subcommittees of CEN/TC 250, e.g., SC 3 for Eurocode 3 (Fig. 3(a)).

2.3 Procedure and strategy of CEN TC250/SC3

The activities in connection with mandate M/515 provided for all Eurocode parts to be further developed or revised in accordance with the directives of the mandate, i.e. (i) improving the clarity; (ii) simplifying routes through the Eurocodes; (iii) limiting, where possible, the inclusion of alternative application rules; and (iv) avoiding or removing rules of little practical use in design. The following principles for the revision and further development of Eurocode 3 were agreed in April 2013 by CEN/TC 250/SC 3 (7), (8):

- preserving the overall structure of EN 1993 and its parts
- improvement of the clarity
- harmonization and simplification of rules (same format, structure, notations, etc.); harmonization of the different parts of Eurocode 3 and with other relevant Eurocodes wherever possible

- reduction of the overall volume (e.g. by avoiding Informative Annexes)
- reduction of the number of alternatives

For the work within the scope of the mandate, a total of 20 parts of Eurocode 3 were summarised in 13 tasks, which are primarily orientated toward the corresponding Eurocode parts. The content was developed in collaboration with the chairs of the working groups of the different Eurocode 3 parts and agreed upon within SC 3. The specific SC 3 contents of mandate M/515 are listed in detail in (9). The two important basic parts EN 1993-1-1 and EN 1993-1-8 were assigned to phase 1 of the mandate in order to create the basis for the revision of all other Eurocode 3 parts at the beginning of the mandate, Fig. 3(b), (c). A further four SC 3 tasks focussing on "stability" were assigned to the early phase 2 of the mandate. The material-specific Eurocode 3 parts, such as EN 1993-1-4 and EN 1993 1-10, belonged to phase 3. Finally, phase 4 of the mandate primarily included the application parts, such as the parts for bridges, silos, masts, or tank structures. The content of the previous part 1-12 for high-strength steels up to grade S700 was integrated into the other parts, part 4-3 was abolished.

Fig. 3. (a) Procedure for the revision of EN 1993, (b) implementation of EU mandate M/515 in 4 phases and (c) new structure of EN 1993.

With a total of 20 parts and approx. 1,450 pages, Eurocode 3 is the most comprehensive series of standards within the Structural Eurocodes. The approach shown in Fig. 3(a) for the revision and harmonization of the rules in EN 1993 was pursued at an early stage; see (10). The so-called Working Groups, which accompany the work in SC 3 from a professional, i.e. scientific and technical point of view, represent an essential element here. The members of the Working Groups consist of experts from the individual member countries for the respective specialist areas. The issues arising in connection with the revision and harmonization of EN 1993 are thus resolved in cooperation between CEN/TC 250/SC 3 and the Working Groups and worked out in the form of proposed amendments. The proposed amendments are then forwarded to CEN for approval and finally incorporated into the European standard or integrated into the new parts of Eurocode 3 as part of mandate M/515.

In addition to the revision and further evolution of the existing parts of the standard, CEN/TC 250/SC 3 decided to develop three new parts of the standard, namely (i) EN 1993-1-13 - Beams with large

web openings; (ii) EN 1993-1-14 - Design assisted by FEM; and (iii) EN 1993-7 - Design of sandwich panels. The new Eurocode 3 “Design of Steel Structures” consists of 21 parts: 14 general parts (EN 1993-1-1 to EN 1993-1-14) and seven application parts (EN 1993-2 to EN 1993-7), Fig. 3(c). The timetable and implementation plan shown in Fig.2 was agreed in SC3. The dates for the CEN Enquiry and the Formal Vote result largely from the respective phases of the standardization parts and the submission dates of the drafts. The timetable is designed in such a way that the parts can be processed one after the other and built on each other so that not all decisions have to be made at the same time. The SC 3 strategy provides for early amendments to correct any editorial and technical errors and to implement mandatory and generally accepted technical adjustments. As part of a first early amendment, necessary editorial corrections are to be made after publication by CEN. Mandatory and generally accepted technical adaptations are to be taken into account in a second early amendment if required. The intention is that the corrections and amendments are already known and approved before the national versions are fully applied in engineering practice. This is intended to avoid irritating engineering practices by making changes immediately after the national implementation of the parts of the standard.

3 SIGNIFICANT CHANGES IN EUROCODE 3

3.1 General

The second generation of Eurocode 3 focuses on the user. The presentation of the rules is intended to follow the workflow in structural design. In addition, application-friendliness and ease of use have been increased, for example, by means of flow charts for structural analysis in EN 1993-1-1 and for the steel selection to avoid brittle fractures in EN 1993-1-10. In addition, formulations have been clarified, and terms, rules, and their presentation harmonized. The latter within Eurocode 3, between the various Eurocodes, and with other European standards, for example, EN 1090-2 when adapting the requirements of the detail categories for fatigue verification of the constructional details of EN 1993-1-9.

The second generation of Eurocodes also aims to make a decisive contribution to the design standards for sustainable buildings and infrastructures for the important future topics of climate neutrality and resource conservation. This will be realized, among other things, by taking into account innovations such as the extension of the scope of application to high-strength structural steels and the improvement of structural efficiency by adapting the design rules. Both will make it possible in the future to increase the slenderness of structures and use fewer resources while maintaining the same structural performance without compromising reliability and violating the principles of durability, robustness, and structural resilience.

Using selected parts of Eurocode 3 and examples, the following sections present significant changes in Eurocode 3.

3.2 EN 1993-1-1

The main objectives of the revision of EN 1993-1-1 were to simplify and clarify the stability design rules, to harmonize the rules between the general part and the application parts, and to reduce the number of alternative design rules, in particular for lateral-torsional buckling. The previous seven options for lateral-torsional buckling verification have been reduced to the three main methods, namely the “standard method”, the “simplified method” and the “general method”. In this context, it should also be noted that two different sets of lateral-torsional buckling curves for the "general case" and the "special case", mainly for rolled and similar welded cross-sections, have been replaced by a new approach (11). Furthermore, of the two alternative methods for beam columns, only "Method 2" of Annex B of the current EN 1993-1-1:2010 was continued in EN 1993-1-1:2022 and extended with rules for mono-symmetric I-sections and capable of considering torsional-flexural buckling and the effect of warping torsion, for example. The content of "Method 1" of the current Annex A was transferred to a so-called CEN Technical Specification, namely CEN/TS 1993-1-101: Alternative

interaction method for members in bending and compression", in order to enable its further application in principle.

The content of the part "Structural analysis", formally in section 5 and now in section 7 of EN 1993-1-1:2022, has been restructured to improve clarity, comprehensibility, and unambiguity. During the evolution, particular emphasis was placed on clearly linking the calculation of internal forces and moments with the verification in the ultimate limit state. In order to counteract the individual and currently often differing interpretation of the rules against the background of national traditions and customs, a flow chart was included in EN 1993-1-1:2022 for the first time for Eurocode 3, Fig. 4. This diagram illustrates the written rules (i) under which conditions the consideration of effects according to second-order theory can be neglected for simplification; (ii) whether and, if so, which imperfections must be taken into account in the computations of internal forces and moments; and (iii) whether stability member checks according to EN 1993-1-1 8.3 should be performed.

Three approaches can be applied depending on the extent and type of consideration of structural deformations according to second-order theory and imperfections:

- a) A complete computation of internal forces and moments according to second-order theory including the consideration of all global and local imperfections, i.e. sway imperfection and member bow imperfection including torsional effects;
- b) A structural analysis and related verification that partly considers second-order effects and imperfections in the structural analysis and partly through individual stability member checks; and
- c) Individual stability member checks of equivalent members, considering buckling lengths corresponding to the overall structural behavior for simple systems (equivalent member method).

These three approaches are described in different methods M0 to M5 and EM. The various methods M0 to M5 are organized in ascending order of complexity; the use of more complex methods is always possible. The most complex method, M5, corresponds to approach a) according to the above categorization. Approach b) comprises methods M2 to M4. In addition, situations in which a cross-section verification with internal forces according to first-order theory is sufficient (method M0).

Keys: LTB – Lateral torsional buckling
 EM – Equivalent member method
 SI – Sway imperfection
 MBI – Member bow imperfection
 MBIT – Member bow imperfection including torsional effects (in-plane and out of plane)

Fig. 4. Methods of structural analysis applicable to ultimate limit state design checks.

3.3 EN 1993-1-2

In order to fulfill the functional requirements regarding the structural performance of a steel structure in the case of fire, two approaches are generally pursued in fire engineering: (1) the prescriptive component-based approach and (2) the performance-based approach for overall structures or subsystems. The second generation of “EN 1993-1-2 - Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1 2: General rules - Structural fire design” provides suitable rules and concepts for both approaches. For that, EN 1993-1-2:2024 incorporates technical changes, extensions and clarifications to improve the ease of use and harmonization of the standard as well as enhancement and innovation by incorporating new findings.

Fig. 5. Level 1 to 3 fire design methods.

The component-based approach focuses on the individual component (column, beam, etc.) or the connection. The associated rules and specifications generally provide detailed information on fire resistance, the use of combustible materials, fire compartment sizes, etc., with the aim of preventing structural failure for a reasonable period of time and avoiding flashover.

The most simple approach for prescriptive fire design are design tables for individual components (Level 1 method), which are usually developed on the basis of fire tests. They are easy and fast to apply, but the scope of application is often limited to a few specific cases. In order to increase the ease of use, the structure of the chapters of the fire design parts of the Eurocodes was harmonized across all materials. As a result, EN 1993-1-2:2024 contains a chapter (Chapter 6) with classified design values in tabular form, although such tabular values for Level 1 design methods are still not an explicit part of EN 1993-1-2:2024.

The most frequently used design methods in fire engineering practice are the so-called simplified design methods (Level 2 methods) for determining the fire resistance of structural components on the basis of standard fires. The easy implementation in engineering practice, as well as their general acceptance and the resulting planning certainty, are advantages of simplified design methods. They are therefore still justified in this age of increasing computer-based design and their further development is of great importance.

The second generation EN 1993-1-2 contains rules for the simplified design of steel components in the case of fire in Chapter 7. For the preparation of the chapter, among other things, the rules for the design of class 4 cross-sections of the previous Annex E were adapted and integrated into the main text, and the scope of the rules was extended on the basis of the results of a European research project. In addition, the rules on lateral-torsional buckling have been modified. The reduction factors for lateral-torsional buckling were revised on the basis of numerical studies, and a formulation consistent with the design rules according to EN 1993-1-1:2022 for ambient temperatures was developed.

An implicit assumption and consequence of the prescriptive component-based approach is that the failure of a component is considered a loss of the load-bearing capacity of the overall structure. However, structures often have sufficient redundancy for alternative load paths in the case of fire, so the inherent fire resistance of global structures is often higher than can be predicted based on the assessment of individual components. A performance-based approach for structures can often solve the shortcomings of the component-based approach and represents a suitable alternative, particularly when simplified approaches become unrealistic, restrictive and/or uneconomical. As part of the

application of so-called advanced design methods (Level 3 method), the first generation, EN 1993-1-2:2010, has for many years offered the possibility of a performance-based design of overall structures (or substructures or individual components) on the basis of natural fire scenarios. This option is updated in EN 1993-1-2:2024. As part of the harmonization, a separate chapter (Chapter 8) has been added consisting of rules for advanced design methods and, as part of EN 1993-1-14, advanced design methods for the structural fire design of steel structures will be integrated into the normative framework for the computer-based design of steel structures based on numerical simulations.

Following the extension of the scope of EN 1993-1-1 and other parts of Eurocode 3, EN 1993-1-2:2024 now covers the fire design of structures made of normal and higher strength steels up to and including grade S700. Detailed information on the temperature-dependent mechanical material properties in the application of natural fire scenarios has also been included for steels up to and including grade S500.

Hot-dip galvanized steel components exhibit low emissivity in the low and medium temperature range. This increases fire resistance and contributes to the realization of unprotected steel structures with low fire protection requirements. The corresponding regulations have been part of the German DAST Guideline 027 (12) and were also integrated into EN 1993-1-2:2024.

The structure of the annexes has been completely revised for EN 1993-1-2:2024. Based on extensive research findings in recent years, Annex C on the fire design of stainless steel components has been completely redrafted. Furthermore, Annex D contains, for the first time, a verification procedure for connections of welded hollow sections. In addition, rules for the structural fire design of beams with large web openings have been included in a new Annex E.

3.4 EN 1993-1-9

The main objectives of the revision of Part 1-9 of EN 1993 were to improve the clarity of the design rules and to link them with the execution rules in accordance with EN 1090-2. The main part of EN 1993-1-9 contained, so far, an extensive set of formulae for the mathematical description of the SN-curves, which is, however, only required for fatigue verification using a cumulative linear damage model according to Annex A. To improve application-friendliness, the second-generation Part 1-9 clearly separates the different concepts for fatigue verification. The main part focuses on the fatigue strength verification according to the nominal stress method using the reference value of fatigue resistance $\Delta\sigma_C$ or $\Delta\tau_C$. All alternative approaches and methods for fatigue verification are dealt with in the corresponding annexes. The basic idea of harmonized SN-curves provides the same slope parameter and number of stress cycles associated with the constant amplitude fatigue limit for all constructional details. This concept has been kept for a long time for steel structure design purposes. In the future, however, non-welded constructional details will be classified more favourably with regard to the fatigue verification curve, and welded constructional details with a large notch effect will be classified less favourably when subjected to normal stresses. The classified constructional details and the associated tables with detail categories are essential to the nominal stress method. The tables have been fundamentally revised in their appearance and structure. The original tables of the current EN 1993-1-9:2010 were created prior to the development of EN 1090-2 for execution considering the concept of tolerance classes as well as EN ISO 5817 and its quality levels for weld imperfections. Hence, the requirements for the constructional details largely lacked reference to EN 1090-2 and EN ISO 5817. The second-generation Part 1-9 establishes this reference. In the current version of EN 1993-1-9:2010, the favorable effects of grinding (more favourable notch detail category) and stress relief can be taken into account in the fatigue verification. In the future, the new Annex F will also allow the benefit of high-frequency mechanical impact treatment (HFMI).

The domain of fatigue assessment is not only important for the structural design of road and railway bridges, crane runways, towers, masts and chimneys, but also represents an essential aspect in the future topics of sustainable mobility, realizing measures to climate change to reach the objectives of the Green Deal and UN's SDGs and ensuring affordable and green energy. For example, increasing the number of wind turbines is a prerequisite to becoming climate-neutral all over Europe in the coming years. Appropriate prognosis models for a realistic service life prediction are required not

least for the assessment and needs-based inspection of existing infrastructures. Advanced fatigue assessment concepts allow the influence of stresses and strains due to operation, cyclic material behaviour and the geometry of the notched components to be explicitly taken into account and, if the relevant data is available, therefore have the potential to provide a realistic prediction of the service life of a steel structure. This means that these models have the potential to predict the service life of new and existing structures realistically and thus to design and assess them economically and reliably. In addition to traditional approaches for fatigue verification in steel construction, advanced approaches are therefore increasingly being applied, i.e. the notch stress method, the notch strain method and the crack propagation method are used as supplements to the nominal stress method and the hot-spot stress method, not least because their implementation in numerical simulation models is increasingly being applied in engineering practice. The new Part 1-14 of EN 1993 will in the future provide normative rules for the design of steel structures using finite element calculations. The new part extensively addresses the simulation-based verification of fatigue strength based on the nominal stress method, the hot-spot stress method and the notch stress method. For the latter method, the second generation of EN 1993-1-9 offers integration into Eurocode 3 and the reliability concept of the Structural Eurocodes for the first time. When determining the nominal stresses, all stress-increasing effects that are not included in the fatigue resistances of the detail categories of the constructional details must be taken into account. For certain geometric influences that are not included in the associated tables, Annex D recommends magnification factors k_1 and stress concentration factors k_f , which allow the simple determination of modified nominal stresses, e.g. Fig. 6 for the constructional detail of plates or girders with thickness transition.

Fig. 6. Distribution of longitudinal stresses for plates and girders with thickness transition.

3.5 EN 1993-1-14

The application of finite element analysis is an integral part of the design of steel structures. Software for structural analysis purposes has been used for many years to compute internal forces and moments, deformations, stresses and strains as so-called system response quantities (SRQs) to a wide variety of actions. The software used is mainly based on the finite element method and often allows a large number of additional elements, such as shell elements, to be used in addition to beam finite elements. Geometrically non-linear calculations, taking into account geometric equivalent imperfections, are carried out for slender steel structures in order to adequately take into account stability effects; and cross-section and member stability verifications are subsequently performed. The elastic critical buckling stress of stiffened plate elements, in particular, is mainly calculated using computer programs. The calculation results are then used, for example, to determine the relative slenderness ratio. In the context of structural fire design, advanced design methods and complex thermomechanical simulations are an integral part of the current generation of Structural Eurocodes and the strength and stability verification of shells are also usually carried out using the finite element method.

The question of why a new part of Eurocode 3 is required for the design of steel structures using finite element calculations, therefore, seems reasonable.

Finite element software suitable for purposes of engineering practice is increasingly available. In addition, engineers today are educated in the fundamentals and application of FE. Therefore, modeling is increasingly understood to mean the choice of finite elements, the use of symmetry conditions through appropriate boundary conditions, and the modeling of supports with contact elements. There are many parallels between the modeling process guided by FE calculations and classical modeling in the context of structural design with pencil, paper, and calculator, including the decomposition of the system into planes, the use of symmetry to reduce the number of unknowns, etc. It is, therefore, important to understand the change in the design process as a chance for structural engineering in general and steel construction in particular. Not least, competencies in the field of modeling must be deepened in training and education. In addition to method- and process-independent modeling, simulation-based modeling should be facilitated. Moreover, the tasks and understanding of numerical simulations, which up to now have predominantly been understood as the input for verification in accordance with Eurocode rules, i.e. analysis requiring subsequent design check, must be expanded, Fig. 7. In the case of direct verifications of the structural performance, often referred to as design-by-analysis, direct resistance check or Direct Design Method (DDM), the verification is an implicit component of the numerical calculation. This results, among other things, in challenges for the independent verification of the design results, such as those already known from the application of the above-mentioned advanced methods in structural fire design. Therefore, a program-independent, uniform terminology for communication, as well as general rules for the design of steel structures using numerical methods and the verification of limit states considering structural reliability according to Structural Eurocodes, are required.

Fig. 7. Approaches of numerical analysis and their characteristics.

4 FUTURE TASKS FOR THE 3RD GENERATION OF EUROCODE 3

4.1 General

The second-generation of Eurocodes, including Eurocode 3 represents a consistent further development of the design standard developed in the late 1990s and at the beginning of the century and is currently successfully applied in engineering practice. In addition to increasing application-friendliness, taking account of and promoting innovations and improving structural efficiency by adapting and further developing the design rules has already supported the significant contribution of the construction sector to reducing resource consumption and climate change mitigation measures. In order (i) to support the high impact of the sector’s contributions to solving global challenges, (ii) to disseminate innovative structural concepts while ensuring quality through appropriate requirements and (iii) to ensure the necessary structural reliability, the committee responsible for Eurocode 3, CEN/TC 250/SC 3, is currently developing a strategy for the future. This strategy is dedicated to the question of which future topics the development of normative rules and guidance is necessary or

useful. On the one hand, the strategy addresses contributions expected from the construction sector by society, such as sustainability in construction and measures to mitigate climate change by promoting circularity through appropriate normative rules for (I) the assessment and retrofitting of existing iron and steel structures and (II) the design of reclaimed steel components for reuse. On the other hand, it addresses technological developments such as (a) big data and artificial intelligence (AI) and (b) 3D printing and additive manufacturing (AM). Finally, (c) the normative guidance of design-by-analysis or the Direct Design Method (DDM) initiated with the new Part 1-14 of Eurocode 3 must be consistently continued and process-related improvement opportunities identified, which, for example, will lead to shorter periods for review and revision of structural design standards and a more vital dialogue with standard committees outside Europe.

4.2 Promoting circularity

Climate change mitigation achievements and the simultaneous contribution of the construction sector to other global challenges, including the associated further increase in construction activities, can only be realized through a systematic combination of different measures and the reasonable use of state-of-the-art technologies. These measures include (a) *rethink* and *reduce* (i) carbon emissions and energy demands during production and recycling, (ii) waste, and (iii) material demands through the development of efficient design rules and innovative construction products; (b) *remanufacture* and *retrofit* of existing building and infrastructures; (c) *recycling* to reduce the consumption of primary resources; and (d) *reuse* of structural components to reduce the environmental impact of production and create circularity in the construction sector, Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Vision of the 3rd generation of Eurocodes.

A key measure of becoming climate-neutral is to establish a circular economy. Its stringent and rigorous implementation results in circular eternity in the construction sector. This visionary approach is to integrate the components of existing buildings and infrastructures into an infinite cycle of (I) *retrofitting*, strengthening and associated enlargement of the service life; (II) structural recycling while retaining material and structural integrity, i.e., *reuse*, and (III) recycling on a material level, i.e., *recycling* and reproduction using innovative and emission-minimized, mostly climate-neutral processes. At the end of use, the structural components are assessed and characterized. The components are categorized in terms of their retrofitting and reuse possibilities: (A) reusable as

components of the existing structure, taking into account retrofitting and any strengthening measures, (B) reusable as components of new structures subject to fatigue loading, e.g. bridge structures, (C) reusable as components of new structures without fatigue loading, e.g. building structures, (D) only recyclable. Starting with largely virtual storage in the existing structural stock, the components are appropriately deconstructed for the new building or infrastructure (urban mining), repaired and improved as necessary, and sent for infinite circles of reuse and recycling, leading to circular eternity. The new structures made from reused components or recycled materials benefit from the advantages of new concepts (*rethink*), e.g., design-for-reuse, i.e., the systematic dimensioning and construction for later deconstruction and reuse, for example, considering easily dismantled connections, and new research and development results (*reduce*), e.g. the application of high-strength steel.

The objective of drafting normative rules for (a) the assessment and retrofitting of existing steel structures and (b) the design of reclaimed structural steel components for reuse offers opportunities and chances for harmonized approaches and concepts, which follow the objective of circular eternity in the construction sector. For the assessment of existing structures, the responsible Working Group 2 of CEN/TC 250 has developed a cross-material Technical Specification, CEN/TS 17440 (13). Its content was recently transferred to a new draft second part of EN 1990 for the assessment and retrofitting of existing structures, EN 1990-2 (14). The committee responsible for Eurocode 3, CEN/TC 250/SC 3, decided in 2021 to develop supplementary material-specific rules for the assessment and retrofitting of existing iron and steel structures and created a corresponding Ad-hoc Group. The scope of a future normative document is to provide supplementary rules and guidance to all existing parts of EN 1993, i.e., general parts and application parts. Hence, these rules will address issues of data-collection and component survey measures, i.e., inspection a/o testing, material properties, structural models and analysis, and reliability and the design of strengthened components. The question of whether normative rules are required for the structural design of reclaimed components for reuse has been the subject of debate. Strong arguments for the decision to develop normative guidance were the advantages of (i) harmonized terminology, (ii) planning and legal certainty in the use of reclaimed components and the realization of corresponding engineering projects in practice as well as (iii) compliance with reliability levels according to the concept of the Structural Eurocodes.

CEN/TC 250/SC 3 recently created an Ad-hoc Group *Reuse*. The Group intends to develop a normative document with supplementary, adapted and amended provisions to various parts of Eurocode 3 for the design of “new” steel structures. These rules are intended to facilitate the structural design of reclaimed steel components, which are to be integrated entirely or in parts into a new construction or a new structural context, including joints, modifications, extensions and strengthening. This future standards document for reuse must be closely coordinated with the rules for assessment and retrofitting, particularly with regard to the component survey and assessment of the existing load-bearing structure. In the first step, rules for steel components that are subject to static loading will be developed. For bridge structures, wind turbine structures, and other structures subject to fatigue loading, the assessment with regard to the possibility of structural reuse of the load-bearing components is more complex. Therefore, rules for components that (a) are subject to fatigue loading or seismic action or (b) will be subject to such loading conditions through reuse will later be added after carrying out corresponding R&D.

5 SUMMARY

This paper has shown the normative evolution for the design of steel structures within the framework of the development of the second-generation Eurocode 3. Selected examples were used to illustrate the implementation of the objectives of increasing application-friendliness through clarity, harmonization, and simplification of the rules. Furthermore, the innovations in Eurocode 3 were presented, in particular, the new Part 1-14 for the design of steel structures assisted by finite element analysis. The consistent further development of this Part 1-14 and the "design-by-analysis" approach are part of the future strategy of Eurocode 3, as are the handling of big data and artificial intelligence

in standardization and design, as well as the design of additively manufactured steel structures. Normative guidance for the assessment and retrofitting of existing iron and steel structures, as well as the design of reclaimed steel components for reuse, is also an essential part of the Eurocode 3 strategy to promote circular eternity as an input to the construction sector's contribution to climate change mitigation measures in line with the SDGs of the UN and EU Green Deal.

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